

Digital exclusion among children and young people: a scoping review

Veslemøy Maria Fossum Johansson, Elia Gabarron, Ingeborg Krange, Ilka Nagel

VERSION 2 – updated to document protocol deviations (march 2026)

REVIEW TITLE AND BASIC DETAILS

Review title

Digital exclusion among children and young people: a scoping review

Review objectives

How do existing studies report children and young people's experiences of digital exclusion in educational and everyday settings?

To further specify the scope of the review, the following sub-questions were added:

1. How is digital exclusion conceptualized in studies of children and young people?
2. What are the characteristics of the existing research in terms of populations, contexts, and study designs?
3. What experiences and dimensions of digital exclusion are reported in the included studies?
4. What gaps can be identified in the existing research on children and young people's digital exclusion?

Key words

Digital exclusion, children and young people, perceptions, education, everyday digital settings, social media

SEARCHING AND SCREENING

Searches

The search will be conducted in Education Source, ERIC, PsycINFO and Scopus. Grey literature will be identified through targeted searches of relevant organisational websites, institutional repositories, and databases.

Study design

Scoping review following JBI methodology

ELIGIBILITY CRITERIA

Population

Inclusion Criteria

- Children and young people aged 10 to 18 years.
- Studies involving broader age groups will be included only if data for the 10–18 age group are reported separately or can be reasonably interpreted.
- The study must focus on the perspectives, experiences, or perceptions of children and young people themselves.
- Studies focusing only on adults (e.g., parents, teachers, professionals) will be excluded unless they also include direct input from children or adolescents.

Concept

This review focuses on the concept of digital exclusion, understood broadly to include a range of structural and experiential limitations that affect children's and young people's access to and participation in digital environments. This includes barriers related to access, such as the lack of devices, connectivity, or digital infrastructure, as well as challenges related to use, including limited digital skills, insufficient support, or a lack of opportunities for meaningful engagement.

Digital exclusion also encompasses exclusion from educational and social digital spaces, such as online learning environments and social media platforms. Related and overlapping terms such as digital divide, digital inequality, digital inclusion, and digital participation are

considered part of the broader understanding of digital exclusion and are included in the scope of this review.

Context

- Educational contexts (e.g., schools, online learning environments).
- Everyday digital settings, including social media platforms and online spaces where children and young people interact socially or informally engage.
- Studies from all geographic regions will be considered.

Types of sources

- Qualitative, mixed-methods, and other empirical studies that explore lived experiences or perspectives.
- Peer-reviewed journal articles, reports, and grey literature (e.g., theses, policy papers) will be included.

DATA COLLECTION PROCESS

Data extraction (selection and coding)

Data from included sources will be extracted using a structured data charting form developed by the review team.

The following information will be extracted:

- Publication details (author(s), year, country)
- Study aim and research questions
- Population characteristics (age, setting, demographic details)
- Conceptual focus (e.g. digital exclusion, digital participation)
- Context (educational, social media, other digital settings)
- Methods (design, data collection and analysis)
- Key findings related to experiences of digital exclusion
- Limitations and implications noted by the authors

PLANNED DATA SYNTHESIS

Strategy for data synthesis

PRISMA guidelines will be followed to synthesise the findings. The data synthesis will follow a descriptive and thematic approach. Extracted data will be summarised in narrative form and presented using tables and figures that map key study characteristics, concepts, and findings. Thematic patterns will be identified across studies, focusing on how digital exclusion is defined and experienced by children and young people across educational and everyday digital contexts.

Analysis of subgroups or subsets

Where possible, subgroup analysis will explore variations in digital exclusion experiences based on age (e.g., early vs. late adolescence), context (e.g., education vs. social media), and participant characteristics (e.g., socio-economic background, disability, or geographical setting). This analysis will be exploratory and used to highlight underrepresented groups or gaps in the literature.

PROTOCOL DEVIATIONS

Minor deviations from the preregistered protocol were made during the analysis stage. While the protocol originally specified a descriptive and thematic synthesis, the analytical approach was further developed into an inductive and iterative basic qualitative content analysis. This adjustment was made to better capture patterns across the included studies regarding study aims, conceptualizations of digital exclusion, and reported findings.

In addition, subgroup analyses planned in the protocol were not conducted due to substantial heterogeneity across the included studies in terms of populations, contexts, and study designs. Instead, variations across these characteristics were described narratively.

Finally, the research question was refined and additional sub-questions were introduced to clarify the scope of the review and to structure the synthesis of findings. The original research question specified in the protocol was:

What is known from existing research about how children and young people experience digital exclusion in educational and everyday digital settings?

During the review process, this was refined into the following research question:

How do existing studies report children and young people's experiences of digital exclusion in educational and everyday settings?

To further specify the scope of the review, the following sub-questions were added:

5. How is digital exclusion conceptualized in studies of children and young people?
6. What are the characteristics of the existing research in terms of populations, contexts, and study designs?
7. What experiences and dimensions of digital exclusion are reported in the included studies?
8. What gaps can be identified in the existing research on children and young people's digital exclusion?

These changes were made to ensure a more appropriate and transparent synthesis of the available evidence.

REVIEW AFFILIATION, FUNDING AND PEER REVIEW

Review team members

- Phd-candidate Veslemøy Maria Fossum Johansson, Østfold University College, Department of Education, ICT and Learning, Norway
- Dr Elia Gabarron, Østfold University College, Department of Education, ICT and Learning, Norway
- Professor Ingeborg Krange, Østfold University College, Department of Education, ICT and Learning, Norway
- Dr Ilka Nagel, Østfold University College, Department of Education, ICT and Learning, Norway

Review affiliation

Østfold University College, Department of Education, ICT and Learning, Norway

Funding source None

Named contact

Veslemøy Maria Fossum Johansson veslemoy.m.johansson@hiof.no

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

This scoping review protocol is registered and openly available via Zenodo. The authors plan to publish the completed review in a peer-reviewed journal. No conflicts of interest are declared. Data extracted during the review process will be made available upon request.